

Paternal strategies in social hierarchy: A comprehensive study on ranked bioenergetic investment and its influence on sperm quality in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*)

Deepali Rahi Roy^{a,1}, Ales Tomcala^{a,2}, Sebastian Pöttsch^b, Annkathrin M. Keiler^{b,c,3}, Sivaramasamy Elayaraja^a, Tram Nguyen Thi^a, Vlastimil Stejskal^{a,4}, Frank Pfennig^{b,*,5}

^a University of South Bohemia in České Budejovice, Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, South Bohemian Research Center of Aquaculture and Biodiversity of Hydrocenoses, Institute of Aquaculture and Protection of Waters, Na Sádkách 1780, 370 05 České Budejovice, Czech Republic.

^b Environmental Monitoring and Endocrinology, Faculty of Biology, Technische Universität Dresden, Zellescher Weg 20b, Dresden 01217, Germany

^c Institute of Doping Analysis and Sports Biochemistry, Technische Universität Dresden, Kreischa 01731, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Strategic reproductive investment
Sperm kinetics
Male-male competition
LC-PUFA
ATP metabolism

ABSTRACT

Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) maintains a stable and long-term social hierarchy in breeding tanks where the dominant male (DM) aggressively competes with subordinate males (SM) for access to the spawning site and the spawning female. An intermediate rank between DM and SM i.e. ascendant male (AM), was identified and categorized. Within this three-tiered hierarchy, we examined a rank-bioenergetic relationship to determine the group-wise energetic investment in reproductive versus metabolic functions and their implications on sperm quality. We analyzed sperm motility kinetics, fatty acids, amino acids, and ATP and its derivatives composition in DM, AM, and SM. Additionally, fatty acid composition along the brain-liver-testes axis, ATP and its derivatives in muscles, body morphometrics, and plasma hormone concentration were assessed. Sperm volume, gonadosomatic index (GSI), testes weight, and testosterone levels were significantly higher in DM than in SM. Among this, testes weight, GSI, and testosterone levels of DM were comparable to AM and collectively differed from SM. No significant difference in sperm kinetics, body morphometrics, and ATP levels in muscle and sperm was found. These results, together with analytical and effect size analysis for fatty acid, amino acid, and energy derivatives of sperm from all hierarchies confirmed our hypothesis that DM and AM preferentially allocate energy towards reproductive function, whereas SM conserve energy, maintaining sperm at a basal physiological level with energetic readiness. Moreover, distinct energy allocation strategies were evident: DM primarily relied on lipid reserves, while AM exhibited elevated levels of specific amino acids, indicating context-dependent metabolic pathways underlying reproductive investment.

Abbreviations: AM, Ascendant Male; ATP, Adenosine Triphosphate; AMP, Adenosine Monophosphate; ADP, Adenosine Diphosphate; ARA, Arachidonic Acid; CASA, Computer-Assisted Sperm Analyzer; DCA, Detrended Correspondence Analysis; DHA, Docosahexaenoic Acid; DM, Dominant Male; DPA, Docosapentaenoic Acid; ELISA, Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay; EPA, Eicosapentaenoic Acid; FA, Fatty Acids; GSI, Gonadosomatic Index; IMP, Inosine Monophosphate; K-value, Nucleotide Degradation Index log-based formula; LC-PUFA, Long-Chain Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids; LIN, Linearity; MUFA, Monounsaturated Fatty Acids; n-3, Omega-3 Fatty Acids; n-6, Omega-6 Fatty Acids; PCA, Principal Component Analysis; PUFA, Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids; SFA, Saturated Fatty Acids; SM, Subordinate Male; STR, Straightness of Trajectory; VAP, Average Path Velocity; VCL, Curvilinear Velocity; VSL, Straight-Line Velocity.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: frank.pfennig@tu-dresden.de (F. Pfennig).

¹ ORCID: 0000-0002-4818-5572

² ORCID: 0000-0002-5232-8441

³ ORCID: 0000-0002-2157-4711

⁴ ORCID: 0000-0002-7892-695X

⁵ ORCID: 0000-0002-2331-2221

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2026.103675>

Received 21 January 2026; Received in revised form 11 April 2026; Accepted 18 May 2026

2352-5134/© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Social hierarchies or dominance-based systems are widespread across mammals, birds, reptiles, fish, and social insects to manage resource competition, mating opportunities, parental care, or reduce predation risk, thereby increasing survival. In fish (including cichlids), the modulation of reproduction tactics in socially ranked animals and its association with behavioural, physiological, neural, or reproductive functioning (Awata et al., 2008; Milewski et al., 2022; Thönnnes et al., 2022) has broadly been studied. Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) is one of the peculiar examples that reside in attribute-based hierarchies, which means the dominant rank in a breeding tank (called a family) is attained through an individual's physical and behavioural qualities rather than age/tenure/inheritance in a group (Milewski et al., 2022). Sexually mature Nile tilapia maintains stable, long-term social hierarchies and is well-known for territorial behaviour in captivity (Pfennig et al., 2012). The sexually mature males fought over and around the spawning site, and the winner became the dominant male (DM) in the family. The guarding, often bigger, and pale body-coloured with much brighter eyes, DM establishes and then maintains the fertilization site, spawns near the site, and defends the spawning female with aggressive fighting and agonistic behaviour against non-territorial, subordinate males (SM) (reviewed in (Beirão et al., 2019)). As soon as the DM claimed its site at the bottom, no other SM are allowed to approach the spawning site, except the female, for courting and spawning. Eventually, when all individuals in the family attain their social ranks, the agonistic behaviour comes down, and the family stays in a stable and long-term hierarchy in order to conserve energy and avoid injury (Maruska, 2014; Pfennig et al., 2012).

Interestingly, in Nile tilapia hierarchies, an upgraded rank of SM has been observed, which we call the ascendant male (AM). Usually, the body size of AM is equivalent to DM but bigger than SM (Ota et al., 2010). In such a situation of stable and long-term hierarchy, with often the presence of AM, it can be presumed that there will be higher competition risk between DM and AM, but low competition between DM and SM, since both groups are incomparable in size. In the presented study, we enquired about the rank-bioenergetic relationship in such gradient-arranged from higher to lower potential reproductive males, giving a special emphasis on the cellular mechanism of their ultimate reproductive outcome - spermatozoa. We ask fundamental bioenergetic questions – for example, whether subordinates (in a stable family) would still invest energy in producing better quality but metabolically costly ejaculates, especially when the sperm will not be used, in this situation of ‘social contraception’ (Sapolsky, 2005). Or what is the role of fundamental nutritional bioenergetics at the organism (bigger and bolder animals versus smaller and shy ones) and at cellular level (sperm; more versus less reproductively active) that contributes to maintaining social dominance among hierarchical animals? How dominant and subordinate males economize the energy synthesis and expenditure on somatic growth versus gamete production in stable hierarchical families?

The relationship between higher levels of long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (LC-PUFA) or omega-3 (n-3) fatty acids in the brain or blood and better cognitive function, boldness, or fertility (and vice versa) has been well documented in mammals (Fedorova and Salem, 2006). However, the association between LC-PUFA bioaccumulation and cognition is understudied and debatable in vertebrates, including fish (Colombo et al., 2013; Spencer et al., 2017). Our recent research performed on the brain-liver axis of bold and shy Eurasian perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) suggested the results (positive association), otherwise (Rahi Roy et al., 2025). Furthermore, the literature has demonstrated the role of fish semen amino acids in basic physiological processes such as metabolism, energy regulation, antioxidant, and osmoregulation (Lahnsteiner, 2009; Zhang et al., 2020). However, only a handful of evidence is available that links the role of semen amino acids or amino acid-derived compounds to communication, signaling, or

behaviour (Krug et al., 2009). In sea lamprey (*Petromyzon marinus*) milt, an odorous polyamine component called spermine was identified (that has also been found in human sperm), which acted as a sex pheromone that attracts ovulatory females (Scott et al., 2019). To the best of our knowledge, no such study has been dedicated to this direction in freshwater fish. Therefore, drawing on examples from higher vertebrates and marine fish, this nascent field must be explored.

With the categorised three different social ranks inside the hierarchy, where AM and SM are reproductively suppressed (no sneaking behaviour was observed), yet could resume an upgrade if DM is artificially removed from the captive population, we hypothesize that SM will prioritise its energy investment in somatic growth and baseline physiological functionality over reproductive performance whereas DM and AM will invest towards reproductive fitness. Therefore, the aim of the presented research is to understand the strategic energetic investment in hierarchically ranked males and its effects on their sperm performance, by providing quantitative and evidence-based data. We selected cells, tissue, and organs from three different fish groups, and their biochemical analysis has been performed accordingly. To understand the fatty acid composition across the brain-liver-testes-sperm axis, we performed fatty acid analysis across the line. We analyzed sperm amino acid content to determine their differential role in fish groups. To determine energy investment strategies on a hierarchical basis, we quantified the ATP content and calculated the K-value (nucleotide degradation) in caudal muscle and spermatozoa across all three studied fish groups. To determine whether there exists morphological, physiological, or sperm kinetic superiority among hierarchical groups, we measured body morphometrics, GSI, plasma hormonal levels, and sperm phenotypic (concentration and volume) and kinetic characters among the hierarchical groups.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animal facility, broodstock keeping, and ethics

Nile tilapia broodstock was established at an animal facility at the Technische Universität Dresden, Germany. Sexually mature males (around 6 months old) were housed in families of 20–30 individuals, with a male:female ratio of around 1:1. Eight such families were maintained in 550 or 820 l individual tanks. The water tanks were maintained at a constant temperature of 26°C and 14 h light: 10 h dark photoperiod. The pH inside the tanks was in a stable range from 6.5 to 7.0. Around 5–10% water was changed daily with fresh water of pH 8.0. The water filters were cleaned weekly, and daily records were kept for water exchange, cleaning cycles, and other important parameters such as temperature, pH, and oxygen saturation. Each tank had a separate water circulation system. Lighting was provided from the upside-down direction (HQI burner 75 W and 5200 K). The original history of broodstock (from Sudan in 1985), animal-keeping facility details, and fish-keeping conditions are also mentioned in (Thönnnes et al., 2022).

Young fish during the first six months were fed ad libitum two to three times daily with a commercial feed (Pro Aqua Brut 1.0 MP, Skretting, Norway). After this period, the diet was switched to F3-P Optiline (6 mm, Skretting, Norway), with feeding reduced to once-a-day ad libitum. During feeding, several small portions were introduced at the top of the tank, where the SM, AM (at the intermediary space), and females were residing, which ensured they always had first access to the food. The remaining food got sink and some part got distributed across the surface by the water current. This allowed numerous fish to reach and eat. Usually, this sinking food was enough for the DM to satisfy its needs. Even if the DM was not satisfied, it could come at the surface to access the food (when added) and then dive back to its territory. This procedure was carried out every day, and sufficient feed was provided to ensure that all animals were adequately fed. Additionally, vitamins (Multivit, hw-Wiegand, Germany) were administered weekly, and trace elements (Tracevit, hw-Wiegand, Germany)

were provided monthly. The health status and activities of the fish were monitored daily. Fish keeping and experimental work were carried out according to the EU directive 2010/63/EU guidelines as well as to the German national regulations and animal welfare (Tierschutzgesetz §11, Abs. 1, no. 1). Fish husbandry and procedures are approved by administrative regulations (Landesdirektion Sachsen, File numbers 25–5131/346/6 and 25–5131/610/9).

2.2. Semi-quantitative hierarchical scoring and family structure

The male hierarchical status was categorized into three groups – dominant male (DM), subordinate male (SM), and an intermediary state, i.e., ascendant male (AM). Hierarchy assignment followed a semi-quantitative categorization framework, which was based on three behavioural or morphological criteria. First, territorial/aggressive behaviour: animals were called “dominant” when they showed dominant and territorial behaviour throughout the observation period and defended the spawning female and spawning site. The SM, on the other hand, showed no territorial behaviour. The AM showed intermediate or opportunistic territorial responses. Second, spatial occupancy: during observation, the fish population was residing in three vertical zones in the tank. The DM remained at the bottom of the tanks and defended their territory. The SM were residing in a group at the top of the tank. The AM swam preferentially in the intermediary space from top (SM) to bottom (DM) and therefore had access to both hierarchical spaces. Third, phenotypic traits: the long-term dominant male (DM) was larger than its conspecifics and displayed the distinctive light coloration of their scales and irises (Pfennig et al., 2012). All the subordinate males (SM), on the other hand, displayed smaller body size, dark body and iris coloration. The AM exhibited lighter coloration and larger body size than typical SM. In some cases of AM, the body size reached the dimensions of the typical dominant ones. The most distinguishing feature of AM (from DM) was their darker colored iris, in otherwise bright looking animals.

The above-mentioned categories of fish, including the females within one tank, were defined as a ‘family’. All the fish in one family were siblings and therefore of the same age. The original photo of one such experimental family and the video of a typical fight between males are presented in Supplementary Fig. 1 and Supplementary Video 1, respectively.

2.3. Behavioural monitoring of long-term stable hierarchies

Initially, fish behaviour across the tanks was monitored and recorded twice daily (during the morning and late afternoon). The key characteristics of the fish (behaviour and appearance) were additionally recorded by sketches and photographs. The animals were identified based on striking individual differences in their pectoral, anal, and tail fins. A clear dominant status was associated with a completely desaturated iris. Although AM may appear bright like a DM, they still exhibit a dark iris. Territorial behaviour of the DM and mating with a female were most pronounced during the afternoon. While in the morning, DM was often seen in the background together with other fish.

Over the time, by consistently reviewing and comparing the records, the dynamic social structure in each family was tracked, and a hierarchical pattern was determined. A family was called a ‘stable hierarchy’ and used for the experiments only when it remained unchanged at least over the period of four weeks. If a system did not show stability for a long-term hierarchy, such a system was discarded from further experimentation. Furthermore, the validity of the classification of male hierarchies was proved by the statistically higher GSI of DM and AM than SM despite the same length and weight of the fish among hierarchies (Section 2.9 and Table 4). The long-term stable hierarchies of males as a model have been established in our facility since several years (Pfennig et al., 2012; Thönnies et al., 2022).

2.4. Sampling of sperm, blood, liver, brain, testes, and muscle

Prior to the experimentation, the body morphometrics (length in cm and weight in g) were recorded. The experimental sampling was divided into two parts: sperm sampling as well as blood and organ sampling. The sperm sampling was completed before sacrificing the fish for organ and blood sampling. To assess the fatty acid distribution and utilization across the brain, digestive, and reproductive line (along with fatty acid accumulation from feed to tissue), the fatty acid analysis was done in the brain, liver, testes, and sperm samples, in addition to duplicate analysis in feed samples, which was common among all the fish. Additionally, rarely explored in fish sperm, amino acid profiling was done in sperm samples. To determine the group-wise energetic investment in somatic growth versus sperm performance, ATP and its derivatives were studied in the caudal muscle and sperm. Finally, to connect the links between fish behaviour and hormone levels, plasma hormone measurements were performed among fish from different social hierarchies. Sampling always started with the lowest-ranking animal and proceeded upwards in the hierarchy. This prevented any potential changes in hormone levels that might occur due to the temporary removal of the higher-ranking male or stress, which could have created an opportunity for a rise in the hierarchy. The experimental design is shown in the Graphical abstract (Fig. 1).

For the sperm collection, the genital papilla was cleaned and dried with a paper towel, and the selected males from each category were stripped by gentle abdominal massage. The sperm samples were extracted with a pipette and a 200 µl tip, kept in a 2 ml Eppendorf, and then kept on ice until motility recording and further freezing (see Sections 2.5–2.8). The sperm volume was noted from each fish.

For the blood and organ sampling, the targeted fish were anesthetized using benzocaine at a dose of 0.2 g/L. Firstly, the blood was drawn from the caudal vein by using a sterilized needle (rinsed in heparin solution) and collected in a 2 ml Eppendorf tube containing 10 µl of 1000 IU/ml heparin. The collected blood samples were then centrifuged (1600 g for 30 min at 4 °C) to separate plasma (supernatant), which was then stored in a –80 °C freezer until further analysis (Section 2.9). Then the fish was sacrificed by severing the spinal cord. Then, immediately, the liver was collected after degutting and separation from the gastrointestinal tract, gall bladder, ducts, and pancreatic tissue. For the brain extraction, first, the head was separated from the body, then the top of the skull was chiseled off with a bone cutter to reveal the brain cavity. The brain tissue was then scooped off. Special care was taken to avoid contamination with the pituitary gland in the brain samples. Brain sampling was continued only after the pituitary gland had been reliably identified and removed (Fontaine et al., 2018; Hollander-Cohen et al., 2022). Afterward, the testes were separated, and their weight was recorded to calculate the gonadosomatic index (GSI) (testes weight/body weight × 100) for each fish. This was followed by a final step of extracting the fish caudal muscle after removing its scales from the localized area. Each sample was weighed separately and stored immediately in a pre-labeled zip-lock bag, which was snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen, followed by long-term storage at –80 °C freezer until further analysis (Sections 2.6 and 2.8).

2.5. Sperm motility and sample preparation for fatty acid, amino acid, ATP, and its related products

The buffered sperm motility activation medium was composed of 40 mM NaCl and 10 mM Tris-HCl, (pH 8.2, and 97 mOsmolkg⁻¹) supplemented with 0.25% pluronic acid (Dzyuba et al., 2019). The sperm motility recording and concentration measurement were done by following previously published protocols (Rahi et al., 2021). Videos were recorded in a phase contrast microscope (Leica DM IRB) equipped with a 10x lens, and the recording was done at 50 frames second⁻¹ (PCC software). The recorded videos were saved in AVI format and later analysed (at 10 s post activation) with ImageJ software and a

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the experimental workflow used in the study focused on Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) socially stratified into dominant, ascendant, and subordinate males.

computer-assisted sperm analyzer (CASA) plugin (Wilson-Leedy and Ingermann, 2007). Sperm motility parameters such as curvilinear velocity (VCL), average path velocity (VAP), straight-line velocity (VSL), straightness of trajectory (STR), linearity (LIN), and motility percentage (%) were analyzed in sperm samples from DM, SM, and AM. The sperm concentration from each male was evaluated using a Bürker cell hemocytometer (Meopta, Czech Republic) and expressed in 10^9 spermatozoa ml^{-1} .

For sperm sample preparation for fatty acid, amino acid, ATP, and its related products, firstly, samples were pre-weighed (weight of eppendorf tube containing sperm – weight of empty eppendorf tube) and the volume was known (in μl) for each fish. For fatty acid and amino acid analysis, the samples with known weight and volume were directly stored at -80°C until further analysis (Sections 2.6 and 2.7). For ATP and its related products, the sample with known weight and volume was taken, and 0.5 ml of ice-cold 3 M perchloric acid (HClO_4) was added to it. The eppendorf tube was vortexed and then stored at -80°C . Later, all the stored samples were transferred (on dry ice) to the Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, University of South Bohemia, Czech Republic, and stored at -80°C until further analysis (Section 2.8).

2.6. Lipid composition and fatty acid analysis in liver, brain, testes, and sperm

Sample homogenization, lipid extraction, and determination of the content by the gravimetric method, fatty acid methyl ester derivatization, and fatty acids profiling with gas chromatography-flame ionization detector were performed according to previously described protocols established in the lab, both for high sample volume, i.e. feed, liver, and testes (Hematyar et al., 2018; Rahi Roy et al., 2025) and low sample volume i.e. brain and sperm (Rahi Roy et al., 2025; Rahi Roy et al., 2024). For quantitatively expressing the fatty acid content in the liver, brain, and testes, the individual fatty acid coefficient was multiplied by

lipid content, which gave the individual fatty acid percentage in g per 100 g. This was further converted into mg g^{-1} . The quantified values for sperm fatty acids were obtained in mg ml^{-1} of sperm, which were then divided by sperm concentration of each male belonging to a specific hierarchy. Finally, the values of sperm fatty acid content were expressed as $\text{mg (10}^9\text{)}^{-1}$ spermatozoa.

2.7. Amino acid analysis

The quantitative analysis of amino acids in DM, AM, and SM sperm (sample volume 10–20 μl) was done by the LC-MS method using the MetAmino kit (Chromservis, Czech Republic). The method used was chloroformate derivatization (Opekar et al., 2021) with slight modifications for fish sperm. First, 10 μl of the samples were diluted with 10 μl of deionized water (a non-activating condition for sperm). Then, 80 μl of precipitation medium (PM-MetAmino kit) was added, and the samples were placed in an ultrasonic bath at room temperature for 5 min. The samples were centrifuged at 7000 rpm, 5 min, 4°C . The supernatant (25 μl ; $\frac{1}{4}$ of the total volume) was placed in a new tube for the Metamino derivatization. The above-mentioned steps ensured that the given amino acids values represented both the sperm intracellular and the seminal fluid pool. Internal standards (10 μl) were added, followed by 20 μl of CTS, and the mixture was vortexed. RDS solution (Reagent Solution) (10 μl) was added and vortexed for five minutes. 400 μl of DWM (Diluting and washing medium) was added to the activated and equilibrated micro-spin filter, and the derivatization mixture was added. After centrifugation and washing step (200 μl of DWM and centrifugation), the micro-spin filter was placed in a new tube and 200 μl of ELM (Eluting medium) was added. Finally, the eluate was transferred to an auto-sampler vial and analyzed. A five-point calibration curve was generated with 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.25, and 0.5 nmol amino acids added to the reaction.

The LC-MS analysis was performed using an Accela 600 coupled to a

linear ion trap mass spectrometer LTQ XL (both Thermo Scientific, San José, CA, USA) for quantitative analysis of amino acids. They were separated on a MetAmino column, 2.1×100 mm (Chromservis, Praha, ČR) with a mobile phase flow rate of $300 \mu\text{l min}^{-1}$, an injection volume of $5 \mu\text{l}$, a column temperature of 35°C , and an autosampler at 10°C . Mobile phases A = 5 mM ammonium formate in water and B = 5 mM ammonium formate in methanol; gradient: 0 min, 55% B; 10 min, 90% B; 10.5 min, 100% B; 12 min, 100% B; 12.01 min, 55% B, 16 min. 55% B was maintained. Positive ion ESI mode detection was used with the following parameters: capillary temperature of 300°C , vaporizer temperature of 300°C , source voltage 4 kV, capillary voltage 40 V; nitrogen served as desolvation gas. Excalibur 2.0 software was used for data processing. The quantified value for each analyte was first obtained as nM/sample, which was further calculated considering the used sperm volume and concentration of each sample. The final values were thus expressed as nM $(10^9)^{-1}$ spermatozoa.

2.8. ATP-related compounds analysis

The protocol for ATP analysis in the fish muscle was followed as already established in the lab (Hao et al., 2021). For the analysis of sperm samples (ranging between 20–30 μl), a standardized protocol from our previous research on Eurasian perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) sperm was followed (Rahi Roy et al., 2024; Veciana-Nogues et al., 1996). Briefly, in the prepared sample tubes (containing sperm and 0.5 ml perchloric acid, see Section 2.5), glass beads were added to each eppendorf tube, and the samples were homogenized using BeatBUG® homogenizer – 400 rpm for 10 s, 2 cycles. The homogenate was then centrifuged in Hettich Micro 200 R centrifuge at 4°C and set to 17000 g for 10 min. The supernatant was collected, and 450 μl of 4 M KOH adjusted to pH 6–7 was added to each tube. The neutralized supernatant was kept in the fridge for 30 min. This step was followed by a second round of centrifugation at 13500 g at 4°C for 10 min. 100 μl of supernatant was collected and used for analysis. Nucleotide assay was done following previously standardized protocol in the laboratory. The HPLC system consisted of the autosampler, thermostatic chamber, UV and DAD detector all Ultimate 3000, Thermo Scientific Dionex (Germering Germany). The separation of analytes was performed on chromatographic column C18 RP Hypercarb 100x 3 mm, 3 μm (Thermo Science) by injecting 7 μl of stored extract. 0.08 M KH_2PO_4 and 0.12 M K_2HOP_4 in water were used as the first mobile phase (A), acetonitrile (HPLC grade) was the second one (B). The flow was 0.5 ml/min, and the gradient chromatography was used as follows: 0–2 min. 100% A, 9–13 min 75% A and 15% B, 13–18 min 50% A and 50% B. After that, 5 min of equilibration was done by 100% A. The temperature of the column was maintained at 35°C , and the UV detector was set to 260 nm. Standards of ATP, ADP, AMP, IMP, hypoxanthine, and inosine were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. The data was processed in Dionex Chromeleon 7.1.2.1713 (Thermo fisher scientific) (Hao et al., 2021). The quantified value for each analyte in fish muscle was expressed as $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ weight of the sample. The value for fish sperm was first obtained as mM, which was further calculated considering the dilution coefficient with perchloric acid and KOH, total sperm volume, and sperm concentration of each sample. The final values were thus expressed as nM $(10^9)^{-1}$ spermatozoa. The final values of nucleotides were used to calculate the K-value, presenting the turnover of nutrients or degradation rate among the fish muscle and sperm samples. The K-value (%) was estimated as $\text{Log}_{10}(\text{Inosine}) + \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Hypoxanthine}) / (\text{Log}_{10}(\text{ATP}) + \text{Log}_{10}(\text{ADP}) + \text{Log}_{10}(\text{IMP}) + \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Hypoxanthine})) + \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Inosine}) \times 100$ (Hao et al., 2021; Rahi Roy et al., 2024).

2.9. Plasma hormone measurement

From the plasma samples, androstenedione, testosterone, 17OH-progesterone, progesterone, cortisol, cortisone, corticosterone, and 11-ketotestosterone were measured. Among them, cortisol and 11-

Ketotestosterone were measured by the ELISA kit (Cayman Chemical, USA), following the standardized protocol in the lab (Thönnies et al., 2022). For the quantification of androstenedione, testosterone, 17OH-progesterone, progesterone, cortisone, and corticosterone, plasma samples were extracted and measured using LC-MS/MS as described before (König et al., 2024).

2.10. Statistical analysis

The sperm-related experiments were conducted on eight families i.e. one fish from each category from eight different families. Dominant and AM were selected as per observation whereas SM was captured randomly. Therefore, eight different individuals from each category were taken as biological replicates. Further, in order to reduce the number of fish sacrifice and to adhere 3 R principal ethically, the organ sampling was done from five different families. For this, one fish from each category from five different families were selected in a similar way. All the analysis performed on sperm and organ samples from each male were made in duplicates and considered a technical replicate. Finally, average data points were derived for each category. Statistical analysis for each experimental part was done in R Studio (version 2023.03.1) and STATISTICA (version ≥ 4.0). The data distribution was assessed by the Shapiro-Wilk normality test. For normally distributed data, one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's *post-hoc* analysis was employed. When data deviated from normality, Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by multiple comparisons of mean ranks was performed. Interactions were considered statistically different at $p \leq 0.05$. Moreover, to quantify the strength of difference between the studied three groups, effect sizes were calculated for all pairwise comparisons using Hedges' g. The effect size analysis was performed on fatty acid, amino acid, and energy derivatives compounds in sperm from the three studied groups. The detailed methods are given in the supplementary file.

As a next step, to validate our results and to identify which parameters are the most decisive for the hierarchies, we chose the significantly different parameters i.e. weight of the testes, GSI, testosterone level, sperm volume, IMP and K-value in muscle, asparagine, threonine, lysine, phenylalanine, aspartic acid, and tyrosine level in sperm. Among fatty acids, ARA, EPA, DHA, SFA, MUFA, PUFA, n-6/n-3 ratio were considered in liver, testes, and sperm. The obtained data was transformed logarithmically and was statistically evaluated using ordination methods as follows: for all data - detrended correspondence analysis (DCA); for linear data - principal component analysis (PCA), redundancy analysis (RDA), and Monte-Carlo permutation test (unrestricted permutations, $n = 999$). In the canonical analysis (RDA), the obtained data stood as variables, and levels of social hierarchy were categorical predictors. The Monte-Carlo permutation test was used to determine statistical significance. Statistic software CANOCO 4.5 (Biometris, Plant Research International, Wageningen UR, Netherlands) was used for the DCA, PCA, RDA, and Monte-Carlo permutation test analyses.

3. Results

3.1. Lipid composition and fatty acid analysis

The lipid reserves, saturated fatty acids (SFA), monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA), and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) content in liver samples of SM were significantly higher than DM and AM ($p < 0.05$). Non-significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in the lipid reserves, SFA, MUFA, and PUFA content in the brain samples of the studied fish groups were observed (Table 1). The results suggest the metabolic differences among behavioural phenotypes, with – SM individuals tending to store more energy (higher lipid reserve) as a coping mechanism against lower food availability, lesser fertilization opportunity, or stress resilience. The DMs, on the other hand, reflect energy reserves spent on gonadal growth or fertilization activities. However, despite the behavioural or metabolic differences, the brain is likely to conserve

Table 1

Fatty acid profile and lipid content of liver, brain, testes, and spermatozoa of dominant (DM), ascendant (AM), and subordinate (SM) Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) males. Fatty acid data is presented quantitatively; mg g⁻¹ weight of the tissue (for liver, brain, and testes) and mg (10⁹)⁻¹ spermatozoa (for sperm samples). SFA: saturated fatty acids, MUFA: monounsaturated fatty acids, PUFA: polyunsaturated fatty acid, n-3: omega-3 fatty acids, n-6: omega-6 fatty acids, n-6/n-3 ratio: omega-6/omega-3 fatty acid ratio. Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation. P-values are derived from parametric (one-way ANOVA) or non-parametric (Kruskal-Wallis) tests, depending on the normality (Shapiro-Wilk test). Separately for each sample type, different letters in superscript indicate a significant difference across columns (hierarchical groups) within the same row and are highlighted in bold.

		Liver			Brain			Testes			Sperm			
		Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate	
Saturated fatty acids (SFA)	C14:0	0.45 ± 0.12 ^a	0.40 ± 0.23 ^a	2.15 ± 0.71 ^b	0.33 ± 0.19	0.34 ± 0.13	0.41 ± 0.09	0.06 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.03	0.14 ± 0.09	3.22 ± 4.41 ^a	17.89 ± 33.93 ^{ab}	15.20 ± 11.56 ^b	
	C16:0	6.76 ± 1.49 ^a	4.97 ± 1.40 ^a	16.98 ± 3.34 ^b	12.64 ± 0.65 ^a	13.01 ± 0.65 ^{ab}	13.66 ± 0.48 ^b	3.06 ± 0.44 ^{ab}	2.93 ± 3.23 ^b	3.79 ± 0.73 ^{ac}	98.61 ± 58.39	218.35 ± 142.09	335.59 ± 271.84	
	C17:0										0.41 ± 0.34	2.30 ± 2.60	1.56 ± 0.98	
	C18:0	3.09 ± 0.66 ^a	2.28 ± 0.59 ^a	6.44 ± 1.09 ^b	11.51 ± 0.54	11.72 ± 0.87	11.57 ± 0.36	1.54 ± 0.27	1.47 ± 0.09	1.83 ± 0.34	74.86 ± 44.69 ^a	152.36 ± 85.89 ^{ab}	252.83 ± 211.47 ^b	
	C20:0	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.05 ± 0.05 ^a	0.53 ± 0.24 ^b	0.14 ± 0.08	0.07 ± 0.10	0.10 ± 0.07	0.00 ± 0.00	0.01 ± 0.01	0.00 ± 0.00	0.64 ± 0.59 ^a	3.21 ± 2.41 ^b	4.63 ± 5.41 ^{bc}	
	C21:0										0.16 ± 0.14 ^a	0.34 ± 0.23 ^{ab}	0.60 ± 0.48 ^b	
	C22:0	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.10 ± 0.08	0.27 ± 0.07	0.30 ± 0.05	0.22 ± 0.13	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.65 ± 0.61 ^a	1.41 ± 0.94 ^{ab}	2.51 ± 1.99 ^b	
	C24:0	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	1.93 ± 0.30	2.12 ± 0.31	2.00 ± 0.20	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.99 ± 1.09	1.32 ± 0.88	2.35 ± 1.86	
	Monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA)	C14:1	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.07 ± 0.03	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	6.71 ± 4.56	14.06 ± 8.70	20.07 ± 16.17
		C16:1	0.51 ± 0.14 ^a	0.40 ± 0.32 ^a	2.91 ± 1.01 ^b	1.34 ± 0.31	1.46 ± 0.25	1.60 ± 0.17	0.09 ± 0.05 ^{ab}	0.05 ± 0.07 ^b	0.23 ± 0.12 ^{ac}	0.38 ± 0.36 ^a	2.99 ± 2.70 ^b	11.44 ± 10.02 ^{bc}
C18:1n-7		1.02 ± 0.40 ^a	0.74 ± 0.24 ^a	2.95 ± 0.70 ^b	1.52 ± 0.22	1.50 ± 0.14	1.59 ± 0.10	0.41 ± 0.06 ^a	0.44 ± 0.04 ^a	0.60 ± 0.08 ^b	11.20 ± 7.48 ^a	20.69 ± 13.78 ^{ab}	45.99 ± 38.73 ^b	
C18:1n-9 trans											0.81 ± 0.75 ^a	1.75 ± 1.17 ^{ab}	3.11 ± 2.47 ^b	
C18:1n-9		7.77 ± 3.98 ^a	5.70 ± 2.83 ^a	30.20 ± 8.29 ^b	17.24 ± 1.85	18.37 ± 1.72	19.27 ± 1.00	1.89 ± 0.34 ^a	1.93 ± 0.11 ^a	3.66 ± 1.05 ^b	30.21 ± 14.22 ^a	65.09 ± 42.13 ^{ab}	115.39 ± 80.54 ^b	
C20:1n-9		0.65 ± 0.43 ^a	0.41 ± 0.24 ^a	2.44 ± 0.74 ^b	0.33 ± 0.14	0.27 ± 0.18	0.34 ± 0.13	0.18 ± 0.02	0.18 ± 0.03	0.15 ± 0.13	0.62 ± 0.68 ^a	2.05 ± 1.48 ^{ab}	3.10 ± 2.32 ^b	
C22:1n-9		0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.33 ± 0.15 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.01 ± 0.11	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.37 ± 0.34 ^a	0.79 ± 0.53 ^{ab}	1.41 ± 1.12 ^b	
C24:1n-9		0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.26 ± 0.16	0.77 ± 0.09	0.83 ± 0.12	0.78 ± 0.04	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.34 ± 0.32 ^a	0.73 ± 0.49 ^{ab}	1.30 ± 1.04 ^b	
Polyunsaturated fatty acids (n-6)		C18:2n-6 trans										0.42 ± 0.39 ^a	0.94 ± 0.59 ^{ab}	1.62 ± 1.29 ^b
		C18:2n-6	3.17 ± 0.99 ^a	2.55 ± 1.05 ^a	13.48 ± 3.82 ^b	1.77 ± 1.35	1.67 ± 0.85	2.18 ± 0.59	1.53 ± 0.22 ^a	1.72 ± 0.17 ^a	2.42 ± 0.58 ^b	10.68 ± 5.45 ^a	24.95 ± 14.02 ^{ab}	38.65 ± 28.99 ^b
	C18:3n-6	0.22 ± 0.25 ^a	0.31 ± 0.21 ^a	1.95 ± 0.61 ^b	0.23 ± 0.31	0.11 ± 0.24	0.31 ± 0.20	0.07 ± 0.03	0.05 ± 0.06	0.10 ± 0.08	0.43 ± 0.40 ^a	0.92 ± 0.62 ^{ab}	1.65 ± 1.31 ^b	
	C20:2n-6	0.25 ± 0.25 ^a	0.04 ± 0.09 ^a	0.78 ± 0.19 ^b	0.13 ± 0.10	0.05 ± 0.07	0.04 ± 0.05	0.24 ± 0.04 ^{ab}	0.24 ± 0.06 ^{bc}	0.16 ± 0.04 ^c				
	C20:3n-6										0.59 ± 0.55	2.22 ± 2.61	2.04 ± 1.25	
	C20:4n-6	1.40 ± 0.55	0.88 ± 0.32	1.56 ± 0.44	2.67 ± 0.21	2.86 ± 0.24	2.82 ± 0.15	1.25 ± 0.33	1.09 ± 0.12	1.13 ± 0.21	22.22 ± 11.53 ^a	47.58 ± 23.10 ^{ab}	79.25 ± 68.01 ^b	
C22:4n-6										11.04 ± 11.04 ^a	29.63 ± 14.64 ^{ab}	50.08 ± 39.92 ^b		
C22:5n-6	1.11 ± 0.64 ^a	0.64 ± 0.27 ^a	3.33 ± 0.80 ^b	0.69 ± 0.37	0.59 ± 0.12	0.72 ± 0.13	0.96 ± 0.13	0.99 ± 0.16		3.58 ± 2.83 ^a	9.81 ± 9.83 ^{ab}	27.17 ± 23.47 ^b		
Polyunsaturated fatty acids (n-3)	C18:3n-3	0.22 ± 0.25 ^a	0.31 ± 0.21 ^a	1.95 ± 0.61 ^b	0.20 ± 0.33	0.11 ± 0.24	0.31 ± 0.20	0.07 ± 0.04	0.05 ± 0.06	0.13 ± 0.11	0.41 ± 0.38 ^a	0.88 ± 0.59 ^{ab}	1.57 ± 1.25 ^b	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

	Liver			Brain			Testes			Sperm			
	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate	
Other	C20:3n-3	0.11 ± 0.11 ^a	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.52 ± 0.20 ^b	0.07 ± 0.10	0.08 ± 0.07	0.08 ± 0.06	0.13 ± 0.02 ^{ab}	0.06 ± 0.06 ^{bc}	0.03 ± 0.06 ^c	0.35 ± 0.33 ^a	0.76 ± 0.51 ^{ab}	1.36 ± 1.08 ^b
	C20:5n-3	0.46 ± 0.16 ^a	0.26 ± 0.23 ^a	0.90 ± 0.19 ^b	0.27 ± 0.09	0.22 ± 0.13	0.31 ± 0.13	0.25 ± 0.05 ^{ab}	0.31 ± 0.10 ^{bc}	0.39 ± 0.09 ^c	10.94 ± 5.23 ^a	24.12 ± 10.76 ^{ab}	43.68 ± 33.76 ^b
	C22:5n-3										545.03 ± 427.29	608.47 ± 435.01	625.31 ± 523.75
	C22:6n-3	8.90 ± 1.94 ^{ab}	6.03 ± 1.53 ^{bc}	10.86 ± 1.60 ^{ad}	17.74 ± 0.90	18.27 ± 1.10	18.54 ± 0.47	3.43 ± 0.69	3.12 ± 0.48	3.16 ± 0.42	75.61 ± 38.16 ^a	151.00 ± 82.86 ^{ab}	236.23 ± 194.87 ^b
	C22:3										10.84 ± 11.12 ^a	29.55 ± 14.48 ^{ab}	48.78 ± 39.71 ^b
	Unknown										17.09 ± 14.44	25.83 ± 18.45	28.49 ± 24.70
	Unknown										64.48 ± 53.09	74.57 ± 53.68	77.11 ± 62.81
	Total	36.10 ± 11.97 ^a	25.98 ± 7.56 ^a	93.72 ± 35.47 ^b	71.82 ± 4.98	73.94 ± 4.35	76.86 ± 3.18	15.14 ± 2.52	14.68 ± 1.41	18.90 ± 3.80	1004 ± 684.06	1537.35 ± 869.15	2082.49 ± 1677.92
	SFA	10.30 ± 2.27 ^a	7.69 ± 2.03 ^a	26.19 ± 5.12 ^b	26.82 ± 0.80	27.55 ± 1.73	27.97 ± 0.55	4.66 ± 0.71	4.46 ± 0.41	5.75 ± 1.13	196.63 ± 119.20 ^a	422.98 ± 270.88 ^{ab}	643.74 ± 528.00 ^b
	MUFA	9.94 ± 4.96 ^a	7.25 ± 3.57 ^a	39.15 ± 11.01 ^b	21.22 ± 2.44	22.43 ± 2.31	23.58 ± 1.33	2.56 ± 0.46 ^a	2.59 ± 0.20 ^a	4.63 ± 1.28 ^b	50.65 ± 26.21 ^a	108.16 ± 59.41 ^{ab}	201.82 ± 145.52 ^b
PUFA	15.58 ± 4.85 ^a	11.40 ± 2.83 ^a	35.34 ± 6.13 ^b	23.78 ± 2.13	23.95 ± 0.76	25.31 ± 1.45	7.92 ± 8.57	7.62 ± 0.84	8.52 ± 1.46	692.80 ± 493.65	931.64 ± 531.09	1159.83 ± 951.37	
n-3	9.69 ± 2.40 ^a	6.61 ± 1.75 ^a	14.23 ± 1.67 ^b	18.28 ± 0.73	18.67 ± 0.94	19.24 ± 0.61	3.87 ± 0.72	3.54 ± 0.46	3.71 ± 0.52	643.19 ± 470.37	814.78 ± 493.88	957.93 ± 788.75	
n-6	6.16 ± 2.59 ^a	4.43 ± 1.47 ^a	21.11 ± 5.31 ^b	5.49 ± 2.04	5.28 ± 1.04	6.07 ± 0.96	4.05 ± 0.68	4.09 ± 0.41	4.80 ± 0.98	48.96 ± 27.21 ^a	116.05 ± 55.18 ^{ab}	200.46 ± 162.53 ^b	
n-6/n-3	0.23 ± 0.12 ^a	0.18 ± 0.10 ^a	1.55 ± 0.64 ^b	0.22 ± 0.10	0.12 ± 0.06	0.24 ± 0.04	0.16 ± 0.2 ^a	0.17 ± 0.01 ^a	0.25 ± 0.07 ^b	0.09 ± 0.05 ^a	0.16 ± 0.08 ^{ab}	0.21 ± 0.05 ^b	
Lipid content (g 100 g ⁻¹)	3.61 ± 1.20 ^a	2.59 ± 0.76 ^a	10.07 ± 2.18 ^b	7.18 ± 0.64	7.39 ± 0.50	7.69 ± 0.45	1.52 ± 0.70	1.74 ± 0.50	1.89 ± 0.72	0.36 ± 0.2	0.70 ± 0.50	0.64 ± 0.45	

homeostasis regulation. In the testes, non-significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were observed for lipid, SFA, and PUFA content, while the MUFA content in SM was significantly higher than DM or AM ($p < 0.05$) (Table 1). In sperm, a non-significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between groups was observed for lipid content. Both SFA and MUFA were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in SM sperm and varied non-significantly ($p > 0.05$) between DM and AM. The PUFA content was comparable ($p > 0.05$) in the spermatozoa of the three studied groups (Table 1). Results suggest a competitively higher demand of SFA/MUFA for sperm production (quantitatively) in SM, while in DM and AM reserve are spent. The fatty acid utilization for qualitative (higher PUFA = higher motility) expenditure is least differentiated among groups.

The omega-6/omega-3 (n-6/n-3) ratio in the liver, testes, and sperm was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in SM (than in the other two counterparts) and non-significantly varied in the brain between all three groups (Table 1). This indicates higher metabolic and oxidative stress and compromised sperm quality in SM.

3.2. Amino acid analysis

There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in total amino acids between the groups. Alanine, arginine, and glycine were the top three amino acids among all groups quantitatively, which together covered 30–50% of the total amino acids. Among essential (indispensable) amino acids, the content of threonine, lysine, and phenylalanine, and among non-essential but functional asparagine, aspartic acid, and tyrosine, varied significantly ($p < 0.05$) between groups. The pattern of changes in the quantitative values among all the mentioned amino acids were the same, significantly higher values in AM, which were comparable with DM, and the lowest in SM sperm (Table 2).

3.3. ATP-related compounds analysis

The ATP and ADP content in muscles and sperm samples among the studied hierarchical fish groups did not vary significantly ($p > 0.05$). The AMP content varied insignificantly in muscles and could not be detected in sperm between the groups. The IMP was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) in the SM muscle than in DM, which was comparable with

Table 2

Quantitative data on amino acid [$\text{mg} (10^9)^{-1}$ spermatozoa] profile of dominant (DM), ascendant (AM), and subordinate (SM) Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) male sperm. Data is presented as mean \pm standard deviation. P-values are derived from parametric (one-way ANOVA) or non-parametric (Kruskal-Wallis) tests, depending on the distribution by Shapiro-Wilk test. Different letters in the superscript indicate a significant difference across columns (hierarchical groups) within the same row and are highlighted in bold.

	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate
Arginine	44.08 \pm 19.83	69.06 \pm 49.02	34.38 \pm 18.98
Glutamine	17.43 \pm 4.09	23.90 \pm 17.39	10.43 \pm 3.30
Serines	18.19 \pm 6.05	29.92 \pm 18.19	15.84 \pm 5.38
Asparagine	6.10 \pm 2.33^{ab}	12.67 \pm 11.23^a	3.97 \pm 1.47^b
4-Hydroxyproline	12.57 \pm 7.52	15.77 \pm 11.68	8.80 \pm 4.32
Glycine	28.60 \pm 8.22	47.74 \pm 35.27	21.72 \pm 5.87
Threonine	7.58 \pm 2.60^{ab}	13.37 \pm 8.81^a	5.38 \pm 1.50^b
Alanine	49.32 \pm 16.00	76.29 \pm 60.42	34.84 \pm 7.32
Sarcosine	6.69 \pm 3.64	11.64 \pm 6.38	4.69 \pm 2.68
Proline	15.37 \pm 8.23	29.34 \pm 28.32	9.50 \pm 2.28
Methionine	5.02 \pm 1.26	7.44 \pm 4.08	3.97 \pm 1.18
Valine	10.55 \pm 3.54	19.38 \pm 9.98	9.39 \pm 2.26
Histidine	15.04 \pm 4.15	22.88 \pm 14.40	10.89 \pm 5.16
Lysine	21.41 \pm 15.05^{ab}	25.89 \pm 10.27^a	11.66 \pm 5.21^b
Phenylalanine	4.12 \pm 2.55^{ab}	9.72 \pm 8.61^a	3.42 \pm 1.11^b
Leucine	13.26 \pm 6.03	24.64 \pm 13.52	10.66 \pm 3.69
Aspartic acid	8.69 \pm 3.07^{ab}	14.03 \pm 7.84^a	7.51 \pm 7.85^b
Isoleucine	-	9.49 \pm 4.39	3.63 \pm 1.73
Tyrosine	12.37 \pm 6.19^{ab}	16.28 \pm 7.85^a	7.24 \pm 3.06^b
Total amino acid	297.82 \pm 94.14	366.20 \pm 240.93	330.97 \pm 231.69

AM. A higher variance in the data suggests individual variability in sperm metabolism across groups. The K-value in fish muscle was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in SM, which is comparable with DM, and lowest in AM. Non-significant difference in K-value was observed in sperm samples of fish groups (Table 3).

3.4. Sperm kinetics and concentration

There was no significant difference in VCL, VSL, VAP, LIN, STR, motility percentage, and sperm concentration between the three studied groups. The mean \pm standard deviation data for DM, AM, and SM is as provided respectively: VCL (57.41 \pm 11.54, 53.12 \pm 11.37, and 56.53 \pm 7.76 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$), VSL (27.96 \pm 9.00, 21.38 \pm 7.06, and 24.95 \pm 9.01 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$), VAP (36.21 \pm 11.54, 29.34 \pm 8.47, and 32.49 \pm 9.84 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$), LIN (77 \pm 6, 72 \pm 11, and 75 \pm 8%), STR (77 \pm 6, 72 \pm 11, and 75 \pm 8%), motility percentage (78 \pm 22, 73 \pm 20, and 77 \pm 14%), and sperm concentration [1.08 \pm 0.37, 0.98 \pm 0.36, and 0.66 \pm 0.10 /10⁹ spermatozoa (ml)⁻¹]. The sperm volume varied significantly among all three groups: highest in DM (708.33 \pm 22.166.87 μl), then AM (291 \pm 34.34 μl), and lowest in SM (111.94 \pm 22.16 μl).

3.5. Body morphometrics and plasma hormone levels

The length and body weight of DM, AM, and SM followed the expected trend of highest values in DM followed by AM, and then SM; however, varied insignificantly ($p > 0.05$) among each other. The testes weight followed the trend i.e. DM>AM>SM. The DM with AM and AM with SM was insignificantly indifferent from each other but the DM was significantly higher than SM (Table 4). The GSI followed the same trend i.e. DM>AM>SM. But the GSI of DM was statistically similar to AM, which together differed from SM (Table 4). Among the studied hormones, only testosterone varied significantly among fish groups. The statistically significant trend was similar to testes weight (Table 4). Generally, SM was characterized by a low level of androgens (androstenedione, testosterone, 11-Ketotestosterone) and progesterone and higher level of cortisol compared with DM and SM.

3.6. Ordination analysis

The lengths of the gradients did not reach the 1.6 value; therefore, the DCA analysis revealed the linearity of the dataset (Supplementary Table 1). In the PCA, the x-axis explained the variability of the dataset by 54.5% and the y-axis by 31.4%. The more different the samples, the bigger their distances are, and vice versa. The SM group is grouped on the right of the diagram and is marked in yellow. The differences between the DM and AM groups were not so strong, which suggests low/no competition between DM and AM. Furthermore, the DM group was more uniform than the AM group (Supplementary Table 2, Fig. 2).

The graphical output of RDA fits the variables to the diagram from 50% (Fig. 3). The distribution of studied parameters closely resembles the PCA diagram. The RDA results also align with the previously obtained results, underlining the physiological reflection of hierarchical groups. The DM, the only reproducing male, has the highest sperm volume, testes weight, and testosterone level. This reflects a huge investment of energy in reproduction. The higher GSI mirrors the testes weight, and the high level of IMP in muscles in the AM and DM groups could be because of active territorial fights. On the other hand, the accumulation of energy in the SM group is obvious by elevated levels of fatty acids in the liver. The higher n-6/n-3 ratio in SM also points to such metabolism, prioritising accumulating storage lipids over investing in sperm cell functional lipids. Furthermore, since the fatty acids for the sperm cells are produced in the testes themselves, the increased level of testes MUFAs as precursors for structural lipids in the SM group indicates lower sperm synthesis. Statistical results are provided in Supplementary Table 3.

Table 3

Nucleotide [mg (10⁹)⁻¹] profile of muscle and spermatozoa of dominant (DM), ascendant (AM), and subordinate (SM) Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) males. Data is presented quantitatively; $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for muscle and $\text{nmol (10}^9\text{)}^{-1}$ spermatozoa for sperm samples. Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation. P-values are derived from parametric (one-way ANOVA) or non-parametric (Kruskal-Wallis) tests, depending on the normality (Shapiro-Wilk test). Separately for each sample type, different letters in superscript indicate a significant difference across columns (hierarchical groups) within the same row and are highlighted in bold.

	Caudal muscle			Sperm		
	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate
Energy-yielding nucleotides						
ATP	0.67 \pm 0.16	0.91 \pm 0.20	0.62 \pm 0.22	39.98 \pm 28.17	73.67 \pm 60.81	57.71 \pm 31.16
ADP	0.32 \pm 0.11	0.28 \pm 0.10	0.24 \pm 0.04	27.16 \pm 19.18	34.33 \pm 21.61	39.98 \pm 36.87
AMP	0.29 \pm 0.06	0.26 \pm 0.04	0.31 \pm 0.04	-	-	-
IMP	1.10 \pm 0.32^a	1.05 \pm 0.25^a	0.23 \pm 0.28^b	24.45 \pm 14.23	25.26 \pm 12.91	25.54 \pm 8.40
Nucleotide degradation products						
Inosine	-	-	1.26 \pm 0.19	201.42 \pm 286.21	254.30 \pm 449.33	759.17 \pm 822.79
Hypoxanthine	-	-	-	45.11 \pm 72.09	20.52 \pm 12.14	17.29 \pm 7.60
K-value	1.71 \pm 0.47^{ab}	1.58 \pm 0.31^b	2.79 \pm 1.03^{ac}	43.59 \pm 8.67	39.19 \pm 3.74	43.24 \pm 5.48

Table 4

Body morphometrics and plasma hormone levels of dominant (DM), ascendant (AM), and subordinate (SM) Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) males. Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation. P-values are derived from parametric (one-way ANOVA) or non-parametric (Kruskal-Wallis) tests, depending on the normality (Shapiro-Wilk test). Different letters in the superscript indicate a significant difference across columns (hierarchical groups) within the same row and are highlighted in bold.

	Dominant	Ascendant	Subordinate
Body length (cm)	36.00 \pm 5.00	33.20 \pm 3.91	30.45 \pm 2.05
Body weight (g)	691.40	559.60	473.10
	\pm 276.65	\pm 192.91	\pm 89.58
Testes weight (g)	2.50 \pm 1.11^a	1.60 \pm 0.45^{ab}	0.47 \pm 0.14^{bc}
GSI (%)	0.36 \pm 0.03^a	0.31 \pm 0.13^{ab}	0.10 \pm 0.02^c
Androstenedione (ng/ml)	7.10 \pm 4.73	5.28 \pm 3.74	0.83 \pm 0.48
Testosterone (ng/ml)	29.95	23.98	5.06 \pm 2.91^{bc}
	\pm 11.25 ^a	\pm 15.65 ^{ab}	
11-Ketotestosterone (ng/ml)	1.63 \pm 0.48	1.62 \pm 1.25	0.29 \pm 0.12
17OH-Progesterone (ng/ml)	6.54 \pm 5.86	6.21 \pm 5.98	0.31 \pm 0.15
Progesterone (ng/ml)	2.75 \pm 2.18	3.09 \pm 2.73	0.33 \pm 0.14
Cortisol (ng/ml)	20.42 \pm 17.76	23.40 \pm 9.75	46.28 \pm 18.16
Cortisone (ng/ml)	16.85 \pm 4.98	15.55 \pm 4.88	12.74 \pm 3.79
Corticosterone (ng/ml)	0.61 \pm 0.49	0.87 \pm 0.21	1.06 \pm 0.32

4. Discussions

4.1. Fatty acids utilization in brain, liver, testes, and sperm

Firstly, the results from brain fatty acids reject any associations between LC-PUFA or n-3 fatty acids in the brain and better cognitive/aggressive function, or reproductive superiority (high sperm volume). This was supported by our previous results i.e., no statistically significant difference in overall fatty acid profile or LC-PUFA of the brain between bold and shy Eurasian perch was found (Rahi Roy et al., 2025).

Furthermore, the results on hepatic and reproductive (testes and sperm) fatty acid analysis suggested a contrasting energy budgeting strategy by fatty acid metabolism between groups. The significantly higher lipid reserves, SFA, MUFA, and PUFA in the SM liver reflect lesser energy turnover, more lipid accumulation, and a conservative metabolic strategy in SM in general (Boonanuntanasarn et al., 2019). This also suggests that SM prefer to retain PUFA for metabolic functions in the liver rather than exporting it to the testes/sperm. However, in DM and AM, the energy reserves are spent. This is justifiable as SM had less engagement in territorial defence, producing energetically costly ejaculates, or getting involved in the fertilization process.

Likewise, a significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) SFA (in sperm) and MUFA (in testes and sperm) content in SM compared to DM and AM as well as an insignificantly variable ($p > 0.05$) PUFA content (in both testes and spermatozoa) in all three groups hints that the DM and AM in the family

prioritise to spend smaller chain fatty acids to produce energetically stable and homeoviscous sperm. Additionally, while PUFA is crucial for membrane flexibility, it is also prone to oxidative damage (Collodel et al., 2020). Significantly similar sperm PUFA in all three groups could be a strategy to prevent lipid peroxidation.

In higher vertebrates, the higher n-6/n-3 ratio has been suggested to be strongly linked with dementia, cognitive decline, and depressive disorders (Loef and Walach, 2013) or lower sperm quality (Liu et al., 2015). The significantly higher n-6/n-3 ratio in SM testes and spermatozoa and a significantly higher ARA: EPA, and DHA content in SM sperm (Table 1) indicates that, even though the SM maintains a better membrane fluidity, yet lowers in the quality markers such as n-6/n-3 ratio or sperm volume. A higher ARA, EPA, and DHA content in SM sperm also suggests better membrane fluidity but at a cost of oxidative stress. Therefore, in order to reach the quality control, SM has been more competitive but at high-risk (Scaia et al., 2020). Additionally, the ratio of ARA: EPA and DHA: EPA did not significantly vary among groups (results not shown). These results reject any possibility of eicosanoid actions (inflammatory/anti-inflammatory actions) based on behavioural phenotypes. However, further validation is needed (see section 4.5).

In a study by Bell and colleagues (Bell et al., 1997), it appeared that docosapentaenoic acid (22:5n-3, DPA) can substitute functionally for DHA within sperm phospholipid classes of two salmonids. In fact, large amounts of DPA were found in sperm from rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*), boar (*Sus scrofa*), rat (*Rattus rattus*), stallion (*Equus ferus*), and rooster (*Gallus domesticus*), together with lower amounts of DHA (Bell et al., 1997). The sperm of blunt snouted mullet (*Mullus barbatus ponticus*), annular seabream (*Diplodus annularis*) showed such peculiarity of a high DPA share, with lower share of DHA (Drokin, 1993). It is interesting that a simple elimination of one double bond from DHA producing DPA (but omega-6; 22:5n-6) results in the loss of several behavioural features in animals as concluded by and Wassall (Stillwell and Wassall, 2003), whereas, multiple species of fish or animal substitute DHA by DPA (but omega-3; 22:5n-3). The biomechanical and physiological function of sperm membrane may remain uncompromised by such substitution. The n-3 DPA can form and substitute for some series resolvins, otherwise produced by DHA (Harwood et al., 2023). This phenomenon is also occurring in Nile tilapia sperm (present study).

Furthermore, two additional peaks were detected in the sperm samples at 25.20 and 44.84 min that were absent in brain, liver, and testes extracts, indicating tissue-specific occurrence. The proposed identities of the analytes eluting at 25.20 min and 44.84 min should be regarded as probable assignments rather than definitive identifications. Their retention behaviour on highly polar cyanosilicone phases, such as BPX-70 or equivalent stationary phases, is consistent with published chromatographic patterns in the peer-reviewed literature. However, without structural confirmation (e.g., GC-MS), these assignments remain tentative.

The peak at 25.20 min is most consistent with a trans/trans or

Fig. 2. Graphical output of Principal component analysis (PCA) performed on following parameters in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) samples: weight of the testes, GSI, testosterone level, sperm volume, IMP value in muscle, K-value in muscle, asparagine, threonine, lysine, phenylalanine, aspartic acid, and tyrosine level in sperm, ARA, EPA, DHA, SFA, MUFA, PUFA, n-6/n-3 ratio in liver, testes, and sperm. Dominant male (in red), Ascendant male (in blue), and Subordinate male (in yellow). The x-axis explains the variability of the dataset by 54.5% and the y-axis by 31.4%. The clear separation among clusters indicates distinct structural differences of SM from DM and AM, while the differences between DM and AM are not so strong.

conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) isomer of C18:2. Highly polar cyanoalkyl polysiloxane phases are well known for their ability to separate geometric and positional isomers of monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids, including multiple CLA isomers (Cruz-Hernandez and Destailats, 2016). This retention range between cis-18:2 and the C18:3 isomers also agrees with the characteristic elution behaviour reported in comprehensive lipid chromatography references (Christie and Han, 2010).

The peak at 44.84 min, eluting shortly after DHA (C22:6 n-3), is most plausibly attributed to an oxidized derivative of DHA, such as a hydroxy-, epoxy-, or peroxidized form. DHA is highly susceptible to oxidative modification, and GC analyses of PUFA-rich samples frequently reveal late-eluting oxygenated derivatives, which exhibit higher polarity and reduced volatility relative to native FAME (Ahonen et al., 2022). The formation of these oxidation products under analytical or processing conditions has been widely documented (Fournier et al., 2006).

To ensure the reliability of data interpretation, these observations should be evaluated in the context of previously published chromatographic studies using BPX-70, CP-Sil 88, SP-2560, and other highly polar stationary phases. If unambiguous identification is found, confirmatory analyses such as GC-MS, hydrogenation tests, or fractionation followed by repeat GC are recommended (Christie and Han, 2010). Because their structures could not be confirmed, only retention times were reported, confirmatory analyses (GC-MS, hydrogenation, or fractionation) are recommended to verify tissue-specific fatty acid composition.

4.2. Amino acid analysis in sperm

Seminal plasma, which actually is a secretion of the testes and accessory glands (seminal vesicle), contains billions of spermatozoa and gives nutrients in the form of glucose, lipids, or, to a minor extent, amino acids (Ingermann, 2008; Vashisht and Gahlay, 2024). While the role of glucose (by glycolysis) or fatty acids (by β -oxidation of fatty acids) in energy imparting through the electron transport chain is of major

importance, and therefore, widely studied (Lahnsteiner et al., 1999, 1998, 1993; Rahi et al., 2021, 2020). The role of amino acids in energy provision takes place only when the substrates from glucose/lipids are limited (that too with compromised protein synthesis) (Hayamizu, 2017). The main role of amino acids is to provide the nitrogen required for nucleotides and their coenzymes, etc. In addition to that, amino acids are also known to contribute to signaling, communication, and chemical cues that affect animal behaviour. In fish (including cichlids), such studies most oftenly have been identified in urine, followed by skin mucus and ovarian fluid (Barata et al., 2007; Dittman and Quinn, 2020; Keller-Costa et al., 2015; Nikaido et al., 2013). However, there is little evidence available in fish semen (Scott et al., 2019).

A non-significant difference in total amino acids between male groups indicates a behaviour-independent role of sperm amino acids. The quantitative values of lysine, tyrosine, aspartic acid, threonine, asparagine, and phenylalanine (in descending order) were significantly higher in AM. These values were comparable with DM and significantly lower in SM sperm (Table 2). These results suggest that all male groups maintain a baseline biochemical capacity in a conserved manner, but the DM and AM strategically elevate specific amino acids to fine-tune their sperm quantitatively and/or qualitatively. This fine-tuning may be linked to quantitative advantage (high sperm volume) or an energetic compensation to maintain a level equivalent to DM. In sperm, these amino acids have a role in maintaining sperm motility, membrane integrity, sperm activation, energy metabolism, osmoregulation, and protein biosynthesis (Butts et al., 2020; Lahnsteiner, 2009). However, further studies will enhance the perspective on the role of sperm amino acids in chemical cues or energetic compensation.

4.3. Energy derivative compounds

From the data on non-significant differences in overall body morphometrics, plasma hormonal levels, and sperm kinetics (Sections 3.4 and 3.5) between the groups, but significantly higher sperm volume, testosterone, and GSI (Section 3.4, Table 4) in DM (and AM) compared to SM, it is clear that these higher hierarchies are preferring to invest

Fig. 3. Graphical output of Redundancy analysis (RDA) performed on following parameters in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) samples: weight of the testes, GSI, testosterone level, sperm volume, IMP value in muscle, K-value in muscle, asparagine, threonine, lysine, phenylalanine, aspartic acid, and tyrosine level in sperm, ARA, EPA, DHA, SFA, MUFA, PUFA, n-6/n-3 ratio in liver, testes, and sperm. Red triangles represent studied groups: DM: Dominant male, AM: Ascendant male, and SM: Subordinate male. Blue arrows indicate direction and strength of variables. The ordination analysis shows clear group separation, with DM and AM associated with reproductive traits, and SM linked to lipid metabolism.

more energy in reproductive line than somatic or metabolic functions. As noted by Pfennig et al. (2012), DM are not necessarily the largest animals in the hierarchy, but the GSI is highest among all DM. Despite differences in the strategic utilization of fatty acids (in liver, testes, and sperm) and amino acids (in sperm) between male groups, the non-significant difference ($P > 0.05$) was seen in the final energetic status (ATP, ADP, and AMP) in fish muscle and sperm (Table 3). The AMP in sperm across all groups even went missing. This shows that the overall energetic state in all three groups is in homeostasis, which means the extra energy needed to maintain dominance is compensated for (by fatty acids or amino acids). More details on group-wise energy compensation are given in the supplementary file. Also, the results show that the baseline and non-significantly different level of sperm ATP (in combination with sperm kinetics) among all the groups is adequate to fertilize the eggs. It means if given the chance, SMs are equally potent for fertilization. Similar results have been discussed by Scaia et al., (2020).

At a further glance, IMP (precursor of AMP/ATP) and the K-value (ATP breakdown index) were significantly higher in DM and AM muscle than their opposite counterparts, respectively (Table 3). This shows that DM has a higher energy reserve for rapidly converting AMP \rightarrow ATP in its muscle, whereas SM has more nucleotide degradation or oxidative stress and a lower energy status. As the dominant fish is the only reproducing, female courting, and aggressive animal in the family (and AM has potential chances for the same), it represents a much larger allocation of energy in DM and AM than SM. The results suggest the following plausible scenario: the overall energy production in DM (and AM) is higher than the SM, but the ATP production in DM and AM is surpassing the consumption, and therefore, the final energetic status is equivalent

among the groups. Overall, there is more efficient energy usage in DM and AM males. Furthermore, it is important to mention that the ATP status of the sperm presents only energy reserves at a quiescent state. To observe the utilization of this energy among groups, one must test the ATP reserves during or after exhaustion of sperm (discussed in supplementary file). In such a low-risk sperm competition population of bluegill (*Lepomis macrochirus*), no differences in the initial (at 0 and 10 s post-activation) ATP levels between parental and sneaker sperm were observed, but the ATP utilization levels varied 20 s post-motility (Burness et al., 2005).

Additionally, at several points, high inter-individual differences were observed, especially in the sperm data, e.g., in some amino acid levels in AM or inosine across all hierarchies. This indicates that, while group-level trends are evident, metabolic profiles are not uniform. However, the analyzed metabolites, such as amino acids and energy derivatives, are highly dynamic. The higher variability across hierarchies could be due to stress handling, differential turnover (higher in DM than in SM), or genuine physiological differences. To validate and assess the meaningfulness of the differences in our results, an effect size analysis was performed on fatty acid, amino acid, and energy derivatives data from sperm across all three hierarchies. Results concluded that while the strategic compensation to sustain higher energy allocation occurred in both DM and AM, but it happens via specific metabolic pathways. The DM compared to the other two groups were utilizing more fatty acids, whereas the AM strategically elevated specific amino acids, which were higher than the other two groups. This context-based energy compensation resulted in minimal group differentiation when seen in the final sperm energetic state (ATP-related data) or kinetics. Detailed results are

discussed in the supplementary file.

4.4. Body morphometrics, plasma hormonal levels, and sperm kinetics

Overall, the results showed that DM and AM invest more energy in reproduction, while SM invests less energy in producing highly quantitative or qualitative sperm because mating opportunities are unavailable. This budget strategy has even led SM sperm to achieve the final energetic (non-significant differences in nucleotides among groups) and phenotypic state (non-significant differences in sperm kinetics among groups) equivalent to DM and AM sperm. These results were supported by another dominant territorial and subordinate non-territorial African cichlid (*Astatotilapia burtoni*) males, which showed that the SM are reproductively suppressed, even though they can attain equivalent sperm velocity and fertilizing ability (Kustan et al., 2012). This cichlid species is a well-researched model for the social ascending process of the dominant male. In contrast to our studied species, which exhibits a long-term stable hierarchy, African cichlid exhibits a rapid and dynamic transition. However, in both models (dynamic and stable), the well-developed gonads of the dominant males in comparison to the subordinate males are reflected in significantly elevated plasma androgen (testosterone) levels and GSI. Alward and colleagues concluded that androgen receptor signaling is necessary for social ascent, this is influenced and overlaid by the social environment and ultimately shaped by the varying sex steroids (Alward et al., 2019, 2020). We assume that these mechanisms also operate in our stable system and account for differences in social standing, even though both groups (DM and AM) have the same steroid hormone levels in our study. In contrast to the presented study, which is the 'social status model', is the sperm competition model in the 'sneaking males' (where subordinates make efforts to reproduce with females sneakily). The sneaking male model, in contrast to the presented one, predicts that subordinates will compensate for the disfavoured reproduction opportunity. This compensation can be done by investing more energy in sperm or by enhancing sperm number or velocity (Dougherty et al., 2022). Future directions and footsteps of our study are discussed in detail in the supplementary file.

5. Conclusion

Our results have shown that with much higher energy allocation, DM and AM prioritise to invest in reproduction rather than metabolic function as in SM. However, the energy compensation in these higher hierarchical groups is more contextual based and follows specific pathways. The energy investments to produce a high-quality sperm were adopted as more utilized lipid reserves in DM and enhancement of specific amino acids in AM. While some sperm quality markers in SM were lower, the sperm still maintained kinetic and energetic thresholds, which were adequate to keep basic sperm physiology. Likely, if given the chance, SM sperm are competent to fertilize the eggs.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Frank Pfennig: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Vlastimil Stejskal:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Methodology. **Deepali Rahi Roy:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ales Tomcala:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Sivaramasamy Elayaraja:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Tram Nguyen Thi:** Investigation. **Potzsch Sebastian:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Keiler Annkathrin M:** Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The project leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871108 (AQUAEXCEL3.0) and the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic, OP JAK – project Aquaculture for Future (CZ.02.01.01/00/23_021/0012616). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. Watch <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T2SwWr1-v3w> for further information on the TNA AQUAEXCEL3.0 project *Alphasperm*. Authors would like to express their special thanks to Prof. Klaus Reinhardt, Susanne Broschek, Dr. rer. nat. Alexander Froschauer, and Ing. Zdenka Machova for their assistance that led to a successful lab analysis. Also, the authors would like to thank the anonymous reviewers for their constructive criticism and comments, which led to improvement of the manuscript.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.aqrep.2026.103675](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2026.103675).

Data availability

All the used data has been attached in the main or supplementary files.

References

- Ahonen, E., Damerou, A., Suomela, J.-P., Kortensniemi, M., Linderborg, K.M., 2022. Oxidative stability, oxidation pattern and α -tocopherol response of docosahexaenoic acid (DHA, 22: 6n-3)-containing triacylglycerols and ethyl esters. *Food Chem.* 387, 132882.
- Alward, B.A., Hilliard, A.T., York, R.A., Fernald, R.D., 2019. Hormonal regulation of social ascent and temporal patterns of behavior in an African cichlid. *Horm. Behav.* 107, 83–95.
- Alward, B.A., Laud, V.A., Skalnik, C.J., York, R.A., Juntti, S.A., Fernald, R.D., 2020. Modular genetic control of social status in a cichlid fish. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 117 (45), 28167–28174.
- Awata, S., Takeyama, T., Makino, Y., Kitamura, Y., Kohda, M., 2008. Cooperatively breeding cichlid fish adjust their testis size but not sperm traits in relation to sperm competition risk. *Behav. Ecol. Sociobiol.* 62 (11), 1701–1710.
- Barata, E.N., Hubbard, P.C., Almeida, O.G., Miranda, A., Canário, A.V., 2007. Male urine signals social rank in the Mozambique tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*). *BMC Biol.* 5 (1), 54.
- Beirão, J., Egeland, T.B., Purchase, C.F., Nordeide, J.T., 2019. Fish sperm competition in hatcheries and between wild and hatchery origin fish in nature. *Theriogenology* 133, 201–209.
- Bell, M.V., Dick, J.R., Buda, C.S., 1997. Molecular speciation of fish sperm phospholipids: large amounts of dipolyunsaturated phosphatidylserine. *Lipids* 32 (10), 1085–1091.
- Boonanuntanasarn, S., Nakharuthai, C., Schrama, D., Duangkaew, R., Rodrigues, P.M., 2019. Effects of dietary lipid sources on hepatic nutritive contents, fatty acid composition and proteome of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *J. Proteom.* 192, 208–222.
- Burness, G., Moyes, C.D., Montgomerie, R., 2005. Motility, ATP levels and metabolic enzyme activity of sperm from bluegill (*Lepomis macrochirus*). *Comparative Biochemistry Physiology Part A Molecular & Integrative Physiology* 140 (1), 11–17.
- Butts, I.A.E., Hilmarsdóttir, G.S., Zadmajid, V., Gallego, V., Støttrup, J.G., Jacobsen, C., Krüger-Johnsen, M., Politis, S.N., Asturiano, J.F., Holst, L.K., 2020. Dietary amino acids impact sperm performance traits for a catadromous fish, *Anguilla anguilla* reared in captivity. *Aquaculture* 518, 734602.
- Christie, W.W., Han, X., 2010. *Lipid analysis: isolation, separation, identification and lipidomic analysis*. Elsevier.
- Collodel, G., Castellini, C., Lee, J.C.-Y., Signorini, C., 2020. Relevance of fatty acids to sperm maturation and quality. *Oxid. Med. Cell. Longev.* 2020 (1), 7038124.
- Colombo, J., Carlson, S.E., Cheatham, C.L., Shaddy, D.J., Kerling, E.H., Thodosoff, J.M., Gustafson, K.M., Brez, C., 2013. Long-term effects of LCPUFA supplementation on childhood cognitive outcomes. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 98 (2), 403–412.

- Cruz-Hernandez, C., Destailats, F., 2016. Gas Chromatography of Fatty Acid Methyl Esters: Resolution Using Conventional and High-Resolution Columns. *Encycl. Lipidom.* 1–4.
- Dittman, A.H., Quinn, T.P., 2020. Amino acid cues emanating from Pacific salmon eggs and ovarian fluid. *J. Fish. Biol.* 97 (5), 1408–1414.
- Dougherty, L.R., Skirrow, M.J., Jennions, M.D., Simmons, L.W., 2022. Male alternative reproductive tactics and sperm competition: a meta-analysis. *Biol. Rev.* 97 (4), 1365–1388.
- Drokin, S.I., 1993. Phospholipids and fatty acids of phospholipids of sperm from several freshwater and marine species of fish. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part B: Comparative Biochemistry* 104 (2), 423–428.
- Dzyuba, B., Legendre, M., Baroiller, J.F., Cosson, J., 2019. Sperm motility of the Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*): effects of temperature on the swimming characteristics. *Anim. Reprod. Sci.* 202, 65–72.
- Fedorova, I., Salem Jr, N., 2006. Omega-3 fatty acids and rodent behavior. *Prostaglandins Leukot. Essent. Fat. Acids* 75 (4–5), 271–289.
- Fontaine, R., Hodne, K., Weltzien, F.-A., 2018. Healthy brain-pituitary slices for electrophysiological investigations of pituitary cells in teleost fish. *J. Vis. Exp. JoVE* (138), 57790.
- Fournier, V., Destailats, F., Juaneda, P., Dionisi, F., Lambelet, P., Sébédio, J.L., Berdeaux, O., 2006. Thermal degradation of long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids during deodorization of fish oil. *Eur. J. Lipid Sci. Technol.* 108 (1), 33–42.
- Hao, R., Pan, J., Tilami, S.K., Shah, B.R., Mráz, J., 2021. Post-mortem quality changes of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) during chilled storage from two culture systems. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 101 (1), 91–100.
- Harwood, J.L., 2023. Polyunsaturated fatty acids: conversion to lipid mediators, roles in inflammatory diseases and dietary sources. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24 (10), 8838.
- Hayamizu, K., 2017. Amino acids and energy metabolism: an overview. *Sustain. Energy Enhanc. Hum. Funct. Act.* 339–349.
- Hematyar, N., Masilko, J., Mraz, J., Sampels, S., 2018. Nutritional quality, oxidation, and sensory parameters in filets of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L.) influenced by frozen storage (–20°C). *J. Food Process. Preserv.* 42 (5), e13589.
- Hollander-Cohen, L., Meir, I., Shulman, M., Levavi-Sivan, B., 2022. Identifying the Interaction of the Brain and the Pituitary in Social—and Reproductive—State of Tilapia by Transcriptome Analyses. *Neuroendocrinology* 112 (12), 1237–1260.
- Ingermann, R.L., 2008. Energy metabolism and respiration in fish spermatozoa. *Fish. Spermatol.* 241–266.
- Keller-Costa, T., Canário, A.V., Hubbard, P.C., 2015. Chemical communication in cichlids: a mini-review. *Gen. Comp. Endocrinol.* 221, 64–74.
- König, S., Rzeppa, S., Thieme, D., Keiler, A.M., 2024. Agreement of steroid profiles in Athlete Biological Passport residues and corresponding serum samples. *Drug Test. Anal.* 16 (8), 761–765.
- Krug, P.J., Riffell, J.A., Zimmer, R.K., 2009. Endogenous signaling pathways and chemical communication between sperm and egg. *J. Exp. Biol.* 212 (8), 1092–1100.
- Kustan, J.M., Maruska, K.P., Fernald, R.D., 2012. Subordinate male cichlids retain reproductive competence during social suppression. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 279 (1728), 434–443.
- Lahnsteiner, F., 2009. The role of free amino acids in semen of rainbow trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss* and carp *Cyprinus carpio*. *J. Fish. Biol.* 75 (4), 816–833.
- Lahnsteiner, F., Patzner, R., Weismann, T., 1993. Energy resources of spermatozoa of the rainbow trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (Pisces, Teleostei). *Reprod. Nutr. Dev.* 33 (4), 349–360.
- Lahnsteiner, F., Berger, B., Weismann, T., Patzner, R., 1998. Determination of semen quality of the rainbow trout, *Oncorhynchus mykiss*, by sperm motility, seminal plasma parameters, and spermatozoal metabolism. *Aquaculture* 163 (1–2), 163–181.
- Lahnsteiner, F., Berger, B., Weismann, T., 1999. Sperm metabolism of the teleost fishes *Chalcalburnus chalcoides* and *Oncorhynchus mykiss* and its relation to motility and viability. *J. Exp. Zool.* 284 (4), 454–465.
- Liu, Q., Zhou, Y., Duan, R., Wei, H., Jiang, S., Peng, J., 2015. Effects of dietary n-6: n-3 fatty acid ratio and vitamin E on semen quality, fatty acid composition and antioxidant status in boars. *Anim. Reprod. Sci.* 162, 11–19.
- Loef, M., Walach, H., 2013. The omega-6/omega-3 ratio and dementia or cognitive decline: a systematic review on human studies and biological evidence. *J. Nutr. Gerontol. Geriatr.* 32 (1), 1–23.
- Maruska, K.P., 2014. Social regulation of reproduction in male cichlid fishes. *Gen. Comp. Endocrinol.* 207, 2–12.
- Milewski, T., Lee, W., Champagne, F., Curley, J., 2022. Behavioural and physiological plasticity in social hierarchies. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. B* 377 (1845), 20200443.
- Nikaido, M., Suzuki, H., Toyoda, A., Fujiyama, A., Hagino-Yamagishi, K., Kocher, T.D., Carleton, K., Okada, N., 2013. Lineage-specific expansion of vomeronasal type 2 receptor-like (OlfC) genes in cichlids may contribute to diversification of amino acid detection systems. *Genome Biol. Evol.* 5 (4), 711–722.
- Opekar, S., Kvicala, J., Moos, M., Pejchal, V., Simek, P., 2021. Mechanism of alkyl chloroformate-mediated esterification of carboxylic acids in aqueous media. *J. Org. Chem.* 86 (23), 16293–16299.
- Ota, K., Heg, D., Hori, M., Kohda, M., 2010. Sperm phenotypic plasticity in a cichlid: a territorial male's counterstrategy to spawning takeover. *Behav. Ecol.* 21 (6), 1293–1300.
- Pfennig, F., Kurth, T., Meißner, S., Standke, A., Hoppe, M., Zieschang, F., Reitmayer, C., Göbel, A., Kretzschmar, G., Gutzeit, H.O., 2012. The social status of the male Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) influences testis structure and gene expression. *Reproduction* 143 (1), 71–84.
- Rahi, D., Dzyuba, B., Xin, M., Cheng, Y., Dzyuba, V., 2020. Energy pathways associated with sustained spermatozoon motility in the endangered Siberian sturgeon *Acipenser baeri*. *J. Fish. Biol.* 97 (2), 435–443.
- Rahi, D., Dzyuba, B., Policar, T., Malinovskyi, O., Rodina, M., Dzyuba, V., 2021. Bioenergetic pathways in the sperm of an under-ice spawning fish, burbot (*Lota lota*): the role of mitochondrial respiration in a varying thermal environment. *Biology* 10 (8), 739.
- Rahi Roy, D., Roy, K., Tomcala, A., Matousek, J., Mraz, J., Stejskal, V., 2024. Fatty acid and energy (ATP-related compounds) metabolism of Eurasian perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) sperm: Endogenous metabolic strategy. *Aquaculture* 579, 740183.
- Rahi Roy, D., Gebauer, T., Cerny, J., Stejskal, V., Roy, K., 2025. Comparative study of long chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (LC-PUFA) accumulation in bold and shy Eurasian perch (*Perca fluviatilis*). *Aquaculture* 595, 741598.
- Sapolsky, R.M., 2005. The influence of social hierarchy on primate health. *Science* 308 (5722), 648–652.
- Scaia, M.F., Cavallino, L., Pandolfi, M., 2020. Social control of spermatogenesis and steroidogenesis in cichlid fish: a comparative approach. *Reproduction* 159 (1), R31–R43.
- Scott, A.M., Zhang, Z., Jia, L., Li, K., Zhang, Q., Dexheimer, T., Ellsworth, E., Ren, J., Chung-Davidson, Y.-W., Zu, Y., 2019. Spermine in semen of male sea lamprey acts as a sex pheromone. *PLoS Biol.* 17 (7), e3000332.
- Spencer, S.J., Korosi, A., Layé, S., Shukitt-Hale, B., Barrientos, R.M., 2017. Food for thought: how nutrition impacts cognition and emotion. *npj Sci. Food* 1 (1), 7.
- Stillwell, W., Wassall, S.R., 2003. Docosahexaenoic acid: membrane properties of a unique fatty acid. *Chemistry and physics of lipids* 126 (1), 1–27.
- Thönnés, M., Prause, R., Levavi-Sivan, B., Pfennig, F., 2022. Transcriptomes of testis and pituitary from male Nile tilapia (*O. niloticus* L.) in the context of social status. *PLoS One* 17 (5), e0268140.
- Vashisht, A., Gahlay, G.K., 2024. Understanding seminal plasma in male infertility: emerging markers and their implications. *Andrology* 12 (5), 1058–1077.
- Veciana-Nogues, M., Albala-Hurtado, M., Izquierdo-Pulido, M., Vidal-Carou, M., 1996. Validation of a gas-chromatographic method for volatile amine determination in fish samples. *Food Chem.* 57 (4), 569–573.
- Wilson-Leedy, J.G., Ingermann, R.L., 2007. Development of a novel CASA system based on open source software for characterization of zebrafish sperm motility parameters. *Theriogenology* 67 (3), 661–672.
- Zhang, H., Liu, Y., Zhou, L., Xu, S., Ye, C., Tian, H., Li, Z., Hu, G., 2020. Metabonomic insights into the sperm activation mechanisms in ricefield eel (*Monopterus albus*). *Genes* 11 (11), 1259.